

Project StoryMachine

exploring implications of recommender based
spatial hypertext systems for folklore and the
humanities

Data Management Plan v1

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	6
1.2 Structure of the Document	6
2. Data Summary	7
2.1 Overview	8
2.2 Purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project	8
2.3 Origin/provenance of the data	9
2.4 Summary table of data types	10
3. FAIR data	12
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	12
3.1.1 Persistent identifiers	12
3.1.2 Standards	12
3.1.3 Keywords and controlled vocabularies	13
3.1.4 Harvesting and indexing	13
3.1.5 Naming conventions	13
3.2 Making data accessible	13
3.2.1 Trusted repositories and identifiers	13
3.2.2 Licenses	14
3.2.3 Accessibility	14
3.2.4 Long term availability	15
3.3 Making data interoperable	15
3.3.1 Metadata vocabularies and interoperability standards	15
3.3.2 References to other data	15
3.4 Increase data re-use	16
3.4.1 Documentation	16
3.4.2 Licenses	16
3.4.3 Quality assurance	16
4. Other research outputs	17
5. Allocation of resources	18
5.1 Costs	18
5.2 Long term preservation	18
6. Data security	19
7. Ethics	20
7.1 Ethics and legal issues	20
7.2 Informed consent	20
7.3 Privacy Policy	20
7.4 Accessibility and inclusivity	20

8. Conclusion	21
9. Acknowledgements and notices	21

Executive Summary

StoryMachine is a UK–German collaboration funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) to develop innovative digital infrastructure for preserving, exploring and co-creating folklore. The project brings together expertise in folklore studies, digital humanities, narrative studies, psychology, and computer science across partner institutions including **Hof University of Applied Sciences, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, University of the Arts London, University of Hertfordshire, University of London, and University of Regensburg**. Beginning in February 2025 and running for three years, StoryMachine will combine spatial hypertext and context-sensitive recommender systems to create a kinaesthetic, visual interface that enables users to explore motifs across stories and cultures and to contribute their own narratives. The Aarne–Thompson–Uther (ATU) folktale index and other folkloristic indices will be integrated into the multi modal knowledge base to reveal relationships between stories and identity.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how data generated and used within the StoryMachine project will be collected, stored, documented, shared and preserved. It covers the types of data expected, procedures for ensuring compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, allocation of resources, data security, ethical and legal considerations, and other outputs. The DMP will be updated as the project evolves and as more information about specific data sources and workflow becomes available.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is the first version of the StoryMachine Data Management Plan (DMP). This first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to be completed by Month 6 of the project. It provides an initial description of the datasets that will be collected or re-used during the project and outlines how these data will be shared, archived, and preserved during and after the project.

The DMP is intended to be a living document and the content will be updated and described in more detail as the implementation of the project activities progresses, before any review of the project and at its final stage, in order to reflect adaptations and changes with respect to the first version.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 summarises the data types that the project will reuse or generate and explains how they relate to the objectives of StoryMachine. Section 3 explains how the data will adhere to the FAIR principles, with subsections on findability, accessibility, interoperability and re-use. Section 4 describes other research outputs and how they will be managed. Section 5 outlines resource allocation and responsibility for data management. Section 6 addresses data security. Section 7 discusses ethical and legal considerations, including informed consent and privacy. Section 8 concludes the document.

2. Data Summary

This section outlines the types of data to be collected, re-used, and generated within *StoryMachine*, their relevance to the project objectives, and their sources. The project prioritises the **re-use of existing folklore materials**, their **formal enrichment** through annotation and knowledge-base construction, and **responsible evaluation** to ensure accuracy, interoperability, and ethical compliance.

Data scope and origin:

- **Re-used materials:** Public-domain or legitimately licensed folklore collections, indices, and taxonomies sourced from established repositories and partner archives.
- **Generated data:** Annotated text and multimedia resources, enriched metadata, knowledge-base entries, trained AI models, evaluation datasets, and dissemination materials.

Operational infrastructure:

- **Project documentation** – Stored on University of London SharePoint for controlled collaborative access.
- **Codebase management** – Maintained in the Hof University GitLab GitLab, including version control, issue tracking, and CI/CD artefacts.
- **Model training and hosting** – Performed on Hof University cloud infrastructure and servers, with local storage for intermediate processing; Neo4j is used for the multimodal knowledge base, and the spatial hypertext backend is hosted on Hof University servers.
- **Public website** – Hosted on Hof University infrastructure to disseminate project outcomes.
- **Dissemination channels** – Bluesky, YouTube, and LinkedIn are used for public engagement and outreach.
- **Archiving and preservation** – Publicly released datasets and outputs are deposited with persistent identifiers (Zenodo) where licensing conditions allow.

This integrated infrastructure ensures that *StoryMachine* data is **securely managed**, **traceable in provenance**, and **accessible for long-term reuse** in alignment with FAIR data principles.

2.1 Overview

StoryMachine does not anticipate generating large volumes of new primary research data. Instead, it **will collect** established, legitimately licensed folklore collections such as fairy tales, folktales, legends, ballads, belief narratives, and mythological texts, and enrich them with structured metadata (title, creator, date, place, language, rights), motif classifications, and entity links.

The scope is multimodal, encompassing textual sources (plain text, TEI/XML), audio (oral histories, ballads), images (illustrations, scans, maps), and video (talks, webinars, video games). A controlled motif and hyperlink taxonomy enables cross-collection navigation by linking stories, characters, places, events, and themes across modalities, languages, and regions.

The operational knowledge base runs as a Neo4j property graph on Hof University cloud resources. Public releases will provide standard export bundles for re-use and verification, including Neo4j `.dump` and CSV import packages, GraphML/JSON, RDF/OWL in TTL/JSON-LD formats, and trained models with accompanying model cards. Evaluation data (surveys, interviews, pilot interaction logs) will be collected under informed consent and **pseudonymised** prior to analysis or release.

Alongside datasets, the project will maintain software design documentation and Architecture Decision Records (ADRs) to ensure that key technical decisions are clearly documented and remain understandable throughout the project and beyond.

2.2 Purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project

The project's objective is to preserve, explore and provide access to folklore traditions by interlinking narratives across cultures, languages and media. Re-using digitised corpora maximises coverage and builds upon folkloristic scholarship. Generated annotations and ontology alignments enable FAIR access, semantic search and recommendation; knowledge-base entities support comparative analysis and transparent navigation via spatial hypertext. Evaluation datasets provide evidence for user-centred design, informing interface iterations, cognitive-map visualisations and recommender components. Dissemination outputs (website, Bluesky, YouTube, LinkedIn) broaden impact and community engagement.

2.3 Origin/provenance of the data

Data derive from three streams: **(i)** public-domain or legitimately licensed repositories and partner archives; **(ii)** new data generated by annotation and evaluation; and **(iii)** project documentation and code. For each dataset, the project records source, licence/rights, collection date, acquisition method and transformation steps (provenance). Illustrative sources include the Folklore and Mythology Electronic Texts (University of Pittsburgh), Project Gutenberg (e.g., Grimm; Andersen) and Internet Archive collections, Hathi Trust holdings and Enzyklopädie des Märchens Online. Additional materials may come from legitimate databases compiled by partners, such as Fionn and Folklore Collections databases, Aarne–Thompson/Uther motif lists, Meertens Institute records and curated heroes/villains wikis, always subject to licence checks. Newly created data include annotated motifs and classification hierarchies derived from project workshops, while administrative data comprise project documentation, code repositories and deliverables. All provenance information will be captured in the metadata and will respect licence restrictions and ethical guidelines.

2.4 Summary table of data types

Work package title	Data collected/reused	Data processed/generated	Data type & format
Project management	Names, affiliations, emails of partners; participant lists for meetings; agendas and minutes	Deliverables and progress reports	Text (DOCX, PDF)
Data acquisition & curation	Digital folklore, legends and fairytales from online repositories	Structured data and motif classifications, knowledge-base entries	Text, audio, image, video
Knowledge base design	Folk collections from external repositories; motif indices; existing metadata,	Metadata enriched with StoryMachine ontology; multi-modal links;	Text (XML/JSON-LD), tabular (CSV/XLSX), images, audio, video

	Query to open source knowledge bases	refined motif taxonomy	
model development & evaluation	Seed corpora for model training and fine-tuning (textual and multi-modal models); annotated motifs	Trained models and embeddings; model weights; evaluation metrics	Binary model files, JSON/CSV results
Interface & platform	User interaction logs; recommender feedback; bug reports	Improved user interface; spatial hypertext layouts; demonstration videos	JSON logs, UI files (HTML/JS), images, video
Dissemination and outreach	Communication materials, social media statistics conference presentations	Blog posts, training materials, webinars and recordings, BlueSky and LinkedIn post. Youtube contents	Text, audio, video, slides

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Persistent identifiers

As noted above, StoryMachine will not generate new primary datasets but its knowledge base will provide access to datasets provided by partners. Where possible this metadata will incorporate persistent identifiers (PIDs) to reference these datasets and the repositories will provide advice and support in creating these.

Each user study scenario document will receive a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) through the Zenodo StoryMachine community repository, ensuring these frameworks remain discoverable and citable long-term. Beyond the formal deliverable, PIDs will be assigned to supplementary materials like technical specifications, mockups, and implementation guidelines that support each user study case.

All datasets curated by partners are referenced by DataCite DOIs.

Reports, key results, deliverables, and other relevant datasets will also have a DOI through the Zenodo StoryMachine community repository. Research data will be published in journals and repositories providing a PID and uploaded to the Zenodo StoryMachine community with a persistent identifier.

Training materials published to Hof University cloud are identified by a PID, including the respective metadata and GitLab repository on Hof University.

3.1.2 Standards

StoryMachine will adopt community standards wherever possible: UTF-8, TEI and where relevant METS/ALTO for text; WAV or FLAC for audio; MP4 or WebM for video with accompanying captions; TIFF for masters and JPEG or PNG for access copies of images; CSV (RFC 4180) and XLSX for tabular data with an accompanying data dictionary; RDF/Turtle and JSON-LD for semantic data with stable HTTP URIs; ONNX or framework-native formats accompanied by model cards for trained models; and MARC21 or BIBFRAME when interoperating with library systems.

3.1.3 Keywords and controlled vocabularies

Keywords will combine generic terms (e.g. *folklore*, *fairy tale*, *myth*, *legend*) with controlled categories from the seed motif taxonomy (e.g., Animals, Plants, Environments, Legendary People, Supernatural Beings, Emotions & Feelings). Additional vocabularies, such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings and Getty AAT, will be used to ensure interoperability. Multilingual keywords will be provided where necessary (English, German). User-generated tags will be moderated and mapped to controlled terms.

3.1.4 Harvesting and indexing

The project will ensure that datasets and related materials are accessible and visible to the research community in a sustainable way. At this stage, the exact technical approach for metadata exposure and indexing has not been finalized. The team will explore appropriate options during the project, taking into account available resources, maintenance requirements, and long-term sustainability.

3.1.5 Naming conventions

File names will be descriptive, include the project acronym and date, and avoid spaces or special characters (e.g., `SMK_MotifTaxonomy_v1_2025-07.docx`). Version numbers (v1, v1.1, etc.) will be appended for iterative files. Data identifiers will be included in the metadata; code repositories will follow semantic versioning (e.g., v1.0.0).

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Trusted repositories and identifiers

Public datasets and deliverables will be deposited in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and GitLab. These repositories provide long-term preservation and assign PIDs. Data will be released under open licences whenever possible.

Different classes of outputs will be deposited in appropriate repositories:

- **Knowledge base and metadata:** Structured data will be stored on Hof University servers and mirrored to a trusted digital repository with DOIs.
- **Code and models:** Source code will be maintained in a private GitLab instance. Stable versions will be mirrored to public repositories and archived with DOIs via Zenodo. Trained AI models and embeddings will be stored on Hof University cloud and released under appropriate licences when allowed by source data permissions.
- **Documentation and deliverables:** Documents will be stored on the University of London SharePoint for collaboration. Once finalised, they will be deposited on Zenodo or institutional repositories. Public deliverables will receive DOIs.
- **Datasets from external sources:** Where licensing allows, copies of external datasets will be archived alongside the knowledge base. Otherwise, only metadata and persistent links will be stored.

Some datasets include personal data (e.g. contact lists, survey responses). These will be stored on secure institutional servers and not shared publicly. Access will be restricted to authorised project members and subject to data protection policies.

3.2.2 Licenses

The general policy for data access is openness. All new metadata generated by StoryMachine will be made available according to a CC0 licence. The default licence for data re-used in StoryMachine will be CC BY.

3.2.3 Accessibility

Public datasets will be made available without access restrictions via persistent URLs. Metadata will remain open even if the underlying data have access restrictions (for example, because of copyright or privacy). Embargoes will only be applied when required for publications. When reusing external datasets, the project will respect the original licences and terms of use.

3.2.4 Long term availability

Persistence of data sources is up to the respective dataset provider. The StoryMachine KB (which is the project metadata container) is planned to remain available beyond the project funded period.

Openly published data on trusted repositories will follow the local policies on availability. Since the whole project relies on infrastructures each with robust funding plans and reliable histories, the data should remain findable and available with no end date.

The project website and project internal data, such as the StoryMachine Shared Drive will be available for at least 5 years after the end of the project. The access will be changed to view/comment only after the end of the project.

3.3 Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Metadata vocabularies and interoperability standards

StoryMachine seeks interoperability at both the data and metadata levels. The StoryMachine Ontology will extend CIDOC CRM and align motifs with the ATU index and other folklore classifications. Data will be serialised in interoperable formats such as RDF/XML, JSON-LD and CSV. Alignments will be created to other domain ontologies and vocabulary services, and cross-references will link StoryMachine entities to external resources. Character encoding will use UTF-8. Where possible, the project will adopt data-exchange profiles.

3.3.2 References to other data

As already mentioned, the project has no “own data”: it uses and aggregates data provided by others, which at present cover an incredibly extensive part of the current research on relevant matters. However, if new data repositories appear to be of interest for the project goal, they will be considered for addition.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 Documentation

Each dataset will be accompanied by a README that describes the origin, structure, processing steps and potential reuse. Motif classifications and ontology files will include usage guidelines and examples. A user guide will explain how to access the StoryMachine platform and query the knowledge

3.4.2 Licenses

StoryMachine will follow the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” for all generated data. Data will be shared as early as possible in trusted repositories. Where legally and ethically possible, the project applies CC-BY 4.0 licensing for its outputs by default, while metadata will be available under the CC0 licence. This licensing policy will be implemented in a way that is easily readable both for humans and for machines.

All the project outcomes will be available and usable by third parties for a reasonable period after the end of the project.

3.4.3 Quality assurance

The metadata includes the provision of the information about the data provider, which is in charge of guaranteeing data quality. Documenting quality assurance usually depends on the trustworthiness of the data providers, which is generally extremely high as they are either a public body, or a governmental agency or a well-reputed and trusted research centre.

4. Other research outputs

StoryMachine will produce a range of outputs beyond the datasets described above. These include scholarly articles, conference presentations, posters, training materials (videos, slides, online modules), reports on evaluation and user studies, and software components. All outputs will be deposited in open repositories with DOIs where possible.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs

Data management costs are integrated into the project budget. They cover personnel time for data curation, ontology development, metadata creation, annotation and documentation; storage and hosting costs for servers; repository deposit fees (if applicable); and long-term preservation costs. Partners will explore institutional support for hosting the knowledge base beyond the project's end. Specific budget lines are detailed in the financial plan

5.2 Long term preservation

Long term preservation will be ensured by depositing other project outcomes into trustworthy repositories such as the above-mentioned Zenodo and GitLab.

6. Data security

Personal and sensitive data (e.g. names, contact details, demographic information) collected during StoryMachine will be stored on secure institutional servers with access control, encryption at rest and regular backups. Access to such data will be limited to authorised personnel and governed by institutional data protection policies. Data transferred between partners will be encrypted. For cloud services (e.g. GitLab, Zenodo), two-factor authentication and secure credentials will be enforced. The project will conduct periodic security audits and ensure compliance with national and EU data protection regulations.

7. Ethics

7.1 Ethics and legal issues

StoryMachine does not involve highly sensitive personal data or vulnerable populations. Nevertheless, personal data will be collected through surveys, interviews and mailing lists. All processing will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national data protection laws. Participants will be informed about the purpose of the study, what data will be collected and how they will be used. Data will be stored securely and anonymised where appropriate.

7.2 Informed consent

Participants in surveys, interviews or workshops will provide informed consent. Consent forms will explain the objectives of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, how data will be stored and shared, and participants' rights (including the right to withdraw without penalty). Participants will be given the option to opt-in to future contact or data reuse.

7.3 Privacy and Cookie Policy

The StoryMachine platform and project website will include a privacy and cookie policy that complies with GDPR and ePrivacy regulations. The policy will describe the types of cookies used, the data collected, and how users can manage their preferences. Analytics will be conducted in a privacy-preserving manner.

7.4 Accessibility and inclusivity

StoryMachine will strive to make all outputs accessible. Documents will follow accessibility guidelines (WCAG 2.1) by providing alternative text for images, captions for videos and clear language. Training materials will be available in multiple formats. Engagement activities will be designed to include diverse participants.

8. Conclusion

This Data Management Plan outlines how StoryMachine will steward data in accordance with the FAIR principles and with ethical, legal and security requirements. The project primarily reuses existing folklore collections and generates metadata, motif classifications and evaluation data to create a digital infrastructure that preserves and explores folklore traditions. By adopting persistent identifiers, standard metadata, open licences and trusted repositories, StoryMachine will ensure that its outputs are discoverable, accessible and reusable. The plan will be updated as the project evolves and will guide the consortium in responsible data stewardship that supports long-term cultural heritage research.

9. Acknowledgements and notices

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